

Exploring Osseoperception at the Wrist: Towards an Augmented Sensory Feedback Interface

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Abstract— Regaining impaired sensorimotor functions is still an open challenge. Osseoperception has emerged as a potential sensory feedback modality. However, this phenomenon has been little explored upon stimulation of the distal bones in the upper limb. This study aimed to preliminarily explore osseoperception by applying vibratory stimuli at different frequencies to the pisiform bone at the wrist of four healthy participants. The lowest perception threshold (0.006 ± 0.002 N) was found at 200 Hz and the highest (0.50 ± 0.26 N) at 1500 Hz, frequencies similar to those reported in previous studies on invasive stimulation. This first insight highlights the wrist as a potential point to evoke osseoperception, which could be used to deliver augmented sensory feedback to people with neuromotor impairments.

I. INTRODUCTION

SENSORY information is crucial for motor control of the upper limbs [1]. However, neurological disorders can affect sensorimotor control schemes, thus causing muscle weakness and sensory impairments and affecting individuals when performing Activities of Daily Living (ADL) [2]. Although several technologies, such as exoskeletons, have emerged to assist impaired people in performing motor tasks, these assistive devices may limit human-environment interaction due to a lack of sensory feedback [3], [4]. To improve their usability, different sensory modalities, such as vibrations, electrical pulses, and mechanical pressure, have been employed to deliver environmental information to individuals lacking sensitivity, providing augmented feedback [4]. However, finding modalities for providing effective, fast, lightweight, and non-invasive augmented feedback remains an open challenge.

Recently, bone conduction, that is, transmitting vibrational cues through bones, has emerged as a promising approach to convey sensory information in the form of osseoperception, i.e., auditory or vibrotactile sensations conveyed to the user through bone tissue [5]-[7]. Advantages include low power consumption and weight, quick response time, and the ability to transmit dense information through a single transducer [5]. Osseoperception has been elicited invasively in patients with

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transhumeral amputations, employing a bone transducer and a coupler attached transversally to their abutment [6], and non-invasively at the elbow joint in healthy participants or those with transradial amputations [5], [7]. However, osseoperception has not yet been investigated upon stimulation of more distal bones in the upper limb, e.g., in the wrist.

In this study, we investigated osseoperception in healthy participants by stimulating the pisiform bone in their wrists. Psychometric tests were conducted to evaluate the minimum perception threshold at different stimulation frequencies, providing an initial insight into osseoperception elicited at distal bones.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Participants

Four healthy participants (age between 24 and 28 yrs, all male) were recruited for this study. The experiment was conducted under the Declaration of Helsinki and the guidelines of the Ethics Committee of the Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (Approval No. 10/2023). Prior to the start of the experiment, participants were given instructions and subsequently wore earplugs and noise-canceling headphones, as previous studies have been carried out to assess bone conduction [5]-[7].

B. Experimental setup

The experimental setup, sketched in Fig.1A, consisted of a GUI (MATLAB® 2021b, Mathworks, US), and the following signal generation chain (see Fig.1B): a multifunction DAQ module (PCI 6259, National Instruments, US) was used as a

Fig. 1. (A) The experimental setup: a PC running a Graphical User Interface (GUI), connected to a Function Generator (FG), an Audio Amplifier (AA), and a Bone Transducer (BT). (B) Signal generation chain. (C) 3D-printed support to locate the BT on the pisiform bone. (D) Artificial mastoid response to stimulation during BT calibration with sinusoidal inputs at different amplitudes and frequencies.

Fig. 2. (A) Amplitude thresholds of all participants (P01-P04) per frequency using SAS technique. (B) Average response of all participants during 50 trials of SAS experiment during stimulation at 400 Hz, where the perception threshold corresponds to the amplitude of the 51st stimulus; shaded area represents Standard Deviation (SD).

function generator of desired sinusoidal signals, which were amplified and filtered (AK-170 Audio Amplifier, Hi-fi, CN) and then delivered to the bone transducer (B-81, Radioear, US). The bone transducer was secured to the individual's wrist at the pisiform bone using a 3D-printed support (Fig. 1C), endowed with a Force Sensitive Resistor to measure the pressure force exerted on the bone during the experiment. To ensure correct amplitude and frequency stimulation, the bone transducer was previously calibrated using the Artificial Mastoid 4930 (Bruel & Kjaer, DK), see Fig. 1D [5]-[7].

C. Perception Threshold

We measured, for different vibration frequencies, the amplitude perception threshold (i.e., the minimum perceivable stimulus per participant) upon stimulation of the pisiform bone. On each trial, a standard two-interval forced choice threshold procedure was implemented: the participant was asked to discriminate between a target and a null stimulus (1 s each), separated by a retention interval of 0.7 s. Then, the amplitude of the target stimulus was updated according to the answer of the participant, using a stochastic approximation staircase (SAS) based on parameters found in the literature (more information available in [6]-[8]). Responses to stimuli at 100, 200, 400, 750, 1500, 3000, and 6000 Hz were evaluated.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The lowest perception threshold was found at 200 Hz, with 0.006 ± 0.002 N, whereas the highest one was found at 1500 Hz, with a value of 0.50 ± 0.26 N (see Fig. 2A). These findings agree with those reported by Clemente *et al.* on stump stimulation in transhumeral amputees [6], where the lowest perception threshold was found at 200 Hz (which also coincided with the sensitivity of the hairy skin Pacinian corpuscles) and the highest at 1500 Hz. Moreover, Mayer *et al.* [7] reported a similar trend upon elbow stimulation, with the lowest thresholds across participants found at frequencies below 200 Hz.

Finally, Figure 2B reports the SAS experiment results at 400 Hz, which has been regarded as the dividing point

between vibrotactile and auditory sensations [6]. Our results, encouraging yet preliminary, suggest that osseoperception can be elicited even when stimulating distal segments of the upper limb. We aim at conducting other studies with healthy participants as well as with people with neuromotor impairments to investigate their ability to discriminate between the two sensory modalities (i.e., vibrotactile and auditory), also in functional tasks. Furthermore, we will explore osseoperception for a larger number of stimulation frequencies.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. S. Johansson and J. R. Flanagan, "Coding and use of tactile signals from the fingertips in object manipulation tasks", *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, vol. 10, no. 5, 2009, pp. 345-359.
- [2] N. Lan, C. M. Niu, M. Hao, C. -H. Chou and C. Dai, "Achieving Neural Compatibility With Human Sensorimotor Control in Prosthetic and Therapeutic Devices" in *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2019, pp. 122-134.
- [3] L. Cappello, R. Baldi, L. F. Engels and C. Cipriani, "Noninvasive augmented sensory feedback in poststroke hand rehabilitation approaches", *Somatosensory Feedback for Neuroprosthetics*, Academic Press, 2021, pp. 207-244.
- [4] C. Demolder, A. Molina, F. L. Hammond and W.H. Yeo, "Recent advances in wearable biosensing gloves and sensory feedback biosystems for enhancing rehabilitation, prostheses, healthcare, and virtual reality", *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 190, no. 113443, 2021, pp. 1-19.
- [5] R. M. Mayer, A. Mohammadi, Y. Tan, G. Alici, P. Choong and D. Oetomo, "Temporal and spatial characteristics of bone conduction as non-invasive haptic sensory feedback for upper-limb prosthesis", *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 17, no. 1113009, 2023, pp. 1-10.
- [6] F. Clemente, *et al.* "Touch and hearing mediate osseoperception", *Scientific Reports*, vol. 7, no. 45363, 2017, pp. 1-11.
- [7] R. M. Mayer, A. Mohammadi, Y. Tan, G. Alici, P. Choong and D. Oetomo, "Bone Conduction as Sensory Feedback Interface: A Preliminary Study" in *41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, Berlin, Germany, 2019, pp. 5322-5325.
- [8] N. Prins and Others, *Psychophysics: a practical introduction*. Academic Press, 2016.